

DIGITAL PRESERVATION STORAGE CRITERIA UPDATE

Informing a New Usage Guide for the Community

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Abstract –This poster provides the latest updates on the Digital Preservation Storage Criteria. These Criteria are intended to help with developing requirements and evaluations of preservation storage solutions, to seed discussions about preservation storage, and/or to use as digital preservation instructional material. The latest version of the Criteria, version 4, contains seventy-one criteria grouped into nine categories and mapped to nine standards. . In this version , criteria have been s cross-referenced to international standards that are relevant to Digital Preservation Storage such as ISO 16363 and the ISO 27000 series. The next step is to update the associated usage guide developed in 2020, which covered risk management, independence, bit integrity and cost considerations. The aim of this poster is to discuss and get feedback on the proposals for additions and expansions of the topics in the associated usage guide to be used in practice and implementation.

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I. INTRODUCTION

The Digital Preservation Storage Criteria were inspired by a community discussion of digital preservation storage at iPres 2015 that recognized a lack of available guidance for organizations that either use or provide digital preservation storage. The first version of the Criteria was developed in 2016 and has been refined in iterative versions over the past years based on feedback gathered at conference sessions and through surveys.

The Criteria working group operates by creating a revision of the Criteria and then presenting and workshopping the revisions at relevant conferences and meetings, which then provides feedback to incorporate into a new revision. The working group has also collected feedback via a Google email group in which interested community members can discuss the Criteria (<https://groups.google.com/forum/#!forum/dpstorage>). The Criteria working group is currently extending the latest version (available at: <https://osf.io/sjc6u/>) [2] which will include references

to various international standards like ISO 16363 [3] and ISO 27000 series [4].

The possible audience(s) for the Criteria include digital preservation managers who need to implement and manage digital preservation storage, providers of digital preservation storage services, auditors of digital preservation programs, digital preservation instructors and students, and practitioners in affiliated domains who rely upon digital preservation storage.

The Digital Preservation Storage Criteria consists of a set of criteria or design attributes to consider for a digital preservation solution, and a usage guide that elaborates on preservation storage principles and practices. The Criteria usage guide provides a necessary supplement to the criteria, as basic preservation storage principles and practices are essential for maximizing the usefulness of the Criteria.

II. USAGE GUIDE EXPANSION

Over the next year, the working group intends to expand the usage guide for the criteria. This will include additional content and new sections designed to provide practical assistance to users of the criteria and reflecting feedback from community members. As appropriate, references to international standards will also be incorporated. The following topics are being planned for incorporation into the new version of the Usage Guide:

- Risk Management
- Independence Across Copies
- Bit Integrity
- Auditing
- Change Management
- Service Level Agreements (SLAs)
- Disaster Recovery
- Organizational Policies and Procedures
- Preservation Strategies
- Media Management
- Storage Costs
- Technology Watch
- Vocabulary

The working group believes that additions to the content of the Usage Guide will improve the usability of the Criteria, and we hope this poster will not only publicize the new version of the Criteria, and also provide a means for receiving feedback that can then contribute to an improved Usage Guide version 2.

REFERENCES

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